

Estimated Glycemic Indices, Minerals, and Antioxidant Compositions of Wheat-*Picalima nitida* Composite Flour Blends

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ABSTRACT

Background: Local raw materials substitution for wheat flour is increasing due to the growing market for functional foods.

Objectives: This research aimed at determining the glycemic indices, nutritional composition, and antioxidant potential of Wheat-*Picalima nitida* (WN) composite flour blends.

Methods: The composite flour blends were produced by fortifying wheat flour with *Picalima nitida* flour (w/w) proportions of 100:0 (0-WN), 95:5 (5-WN), 90:10 (10-WN), 80:20 (20-WN), and 70:30 (30-WN).

Results: The composite flours were rich in crude protein, crude fiber, and mineral contents. The sugar content ranged from (14.70 ± 0.04) in 30 % inclusion of *Picalima nitida* flour (30-WN) to (22.21 ± 0.03) in 100 % wheat flour (0-WN) while starch ranged from (33.30 ± 0.03) in 30-WN to (44.65 ± 0.05) in 0-WN. The composite flour had a low eGI ranging from (28.41 ± 0.01) to (52.52 ± 0.03) compared to 0-WN (65.00 ± 0.02). The GL ranged from (12.09 ± 0.01) to (20.76 ± 0.03). 30-WN blends had the highest antioxidant activities and good glycemic potential and thus, may slow down the absorption of sugar.

Conclusion: Carbohydrate foods that are absorbed quickly during digestion have a higher glycemic index and may release their sugar quickly into the bloodstream.

Keywords: Antioxidant, Glycemic index, Wheat, *Picalima nitida*, Composite Flour

INTRODUCTION

The glycemic index (GI) ranks carbohydrate foods based on the rate at which they are digested, absorbed, and increase blood sugar levels over at least two hours, while glycemic Load is a measure of how quickly a given plate of food raises blood sugar levels after consumption. Carbohydrate foods that are absorbed quickly during digestion have a higher glycemic index and therefore release their glucose quickly into the bloodstream (Brouns *et al.*, 2015; Foster-Powell *et al.*, 2002). Low GI foods lengthen digestion due to their slow absorption and may help to feel full. The digestive system breaks down carbohydrate foods into simple sugars (glucose). The glucose is then carried to the bloodstream through the body's cells. The pancreas secretes insulin, a hormone that helps glucose move

from the blood into the cells. Glucose is "burned" with oxygen inside cells to produce energy, ATP. The body converts excess glucose from carbohydrate foods into glycogen. Glycogen acts as a storage form of glucose within the muscle tissue and the liver. A GI scale less than 55 connotes low GI, medium GI ranges from 55 to 70, while high GI is greater than 70. GI of food depends largely on the following factors: size, texture, viscosity, and ripeness of a given food sample. For example, both ripe and unripe bananas have a low GI. An unripe banana may have a GI of 30, while a ripe banana has a GI of 51 (Brouns *et al.*, 2015; Foster-Powell *et al.*, 2002). This may slow down the absorption of glucose into the bloodstream. Understanding the GI and GL of different foods can help make an

informed decision about the meal or diet to be consumed. High GI can be beneficial in replenishing glycogen in the muscles after strenuous exercise (Brous *et al.*, 2015; Foster-Powell *et al.*, 2002). It can also speedily restore blood glucose levels to normal when an individual with diabetes is experiencing hypoglycemia (when the blood glucose levels fall below the normal range of 4-8 mmol/L).

Type-2- diabetes is a chronic noncommunicable disease that occur when the body could not synthesize enough insulin in the pancreas by the beta cells of the islets of langerhans. This could result to insufficient utilization of insulin resulting in spike in blood sugar levels. This may degrades the quality of life of the people living with diabetes (Stancliffe, Thorpe and Zemel, 2011; Rideout, Marinangeli, Martin, *et al.*, 2013; Gbenga-Fabusiwa, Oladele, Oboh *et al.*, 2019).

During digestion food is split down into basic components, carbohydrate are broken into simple sugars (glucose) which is critical source of energy for the body's cells. Insulin traveling in the blood signals the cells to take up glucose. Insulin is a hormone produced by the pancreas. The pancreas is an organ in the abdomen. When levels of glucose in the blood rise after a meal, the pancreas produces more insulin. Type-2 diabetes occurs when the body's cells resist the normal effect of insulin, which is to drive glucose in the blood into the inside of the cell. This condition is called insulin resistance. Thus, resulting in glucose build up in the blood (Stancliffe, Thorpe and Zemel, 2011; Rideout, Marinangeli, Martin, *et al.*, 2013; Gbenga-Fabusiwa, Oladele, Oboh *et al.*, 2019).

The contemporary lifestyle which is characterized by over-consumption of food, decreased physical activity and intense stress results in the constant increase in the occurrence of the disease. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), diabetes is among the ten main causes of death worldwide and in 2016, it led to the death of approximately 1.6 million people (WHO, 2020). Taking measures and developing strategies are of utmost importance both for the prevention and correct management of diabetes. Besides medication, changes in lifestyle is an integral part of preventing and managing the type-2 diabetes.

Several studies have been carried out in support of the fact that a lifestyle characterized by a balanced diet and increased physical activity may prevent against the development of type -2 -diabetes and have a beneficial effect on diabetic patients, impeding or retarding the progression of the disease and the occurrence of complications. Among these stud-

ies are dietary interventions, which have focused on specific food groups, some of which are milk and other dairy products, particularly yoghurt (Stancliffe, Thorpe and Zemel, 2011; Rideout, Marinangeli, Martin, *et al.*, 2013); *legume consumptions*, Gbenga-Fabusiwa, Oladele, Oboh *et al.*, 2019 investigated glycemic response of people living with type -2- diabetes to Pigeon pea-wheat flour biscuits and observed that 30 % pigeon pea -70 % wheat flour biscuits lowers the blood sugar levels.

The plant "Akuamma" (*Picralima nitida*) belongs to the Apocynaceae family. Its leaves are broad (3-10 cm) and oblong (6-20 cm) long with hard, tiny lateral nerves of about 14 to 24 pairs (Duwiejua *et al.*, 2002). *Picralima nitida* is applied in traditional medicine for the treatment and management of malaria, hypertension, diabetes, hepatitis, pneumonia, and abscesses (De Campos *et al.*, 2020; Okonta, Aguwa, 2007) by using various parts of the plants like leaves, seeds, stem, and bark (Akinwunmi, Amadi, 2019). Ojuola, Abatan (2018) worked on the anti-diabetogenic effects of the seed extracts of *Picralima nitida* and reported that 30 % ethyl acetate and 78 % ethanol had the highest blood sugar lowering effects. The phytochemical analysis of the extracts revealed that *Picralima nitida* plant has alkaloids, flavonoids, saponin, tannins and cardiac glycosides. The results from the phytochemical evaluation support the health benefit of *Picralima nitida* for lowering blood sugar in diabetic patients. Dzutam, Kuete (2023) studied *Picralima nitida* as a potential source of antibacterial agents and reported that the plant displayed antimalarial, analgesic, anticancer, and anti-diabetic potentials. Inya-Agba, Ezea, Odukoya (2006) evaluated *Picralima nitida* hypoglycemic and toxicity activities and reported that *Picralima nitida* seed (900 mg/kg) extracts exerted higher hypoglycemic action than glibenclamide (a well-known anti-diabetic drug). The result proves the potency of the extracts in management of diabetes mellitus. The study suggested that *Picralima nitida* lowers blood glucose by probably increasing the permeability of the plasma membrane to glucose. Yao, Assamoi, Antoine, Ouattara, N'dri (2023) studied anti-diabetic potentials of *Picralima nitida* seed powder, an indigenous Ivorian edible plant in type II diabetes mellitus rat model. The team reported that *Picralima nitida* seeds are rich in essential bioactive compounds, which make them useful for food and in the traditional treatment of type-2-diabetes. However, the *Picralima nitida* fruits are highly perishable, thus limiting their uses for a long period towards ready-to-eat, marketable products. None of the researchers utilized *Picralima nitida* seeds in the production of composite flour to maximize its anti-diabetic potentials and reduce the rate of perishability of the fruits. Thus, this study intends to formulate Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour and investigate its glycemic indices, nutritional, mineral, and antioxidant potentials. It is cultivated in Benin, Ghana, the Ivory Coast, Nigeria,

Gabon, Cameroon, Cabinda, the Central African Republic, the Republic of Congo, Zaire, and Uganda (Nwaogu *et al.*, 2015). In Nigeria, the plant is known by a variety of regional names, including Osu (Edo), Osi-Igwe or Ogwadhi (Igbo), and Abere (Yoruba). Aboya (Ivory Coast), Balunyi (Sierra Leone), Kahana, akuama (Aghedo *et al.*, 2021; Alcover *et al.*, 2020). *Picralima nitida* plant is under storey and can reach a height of 3.5 meters and a diameter of 60 centimeters when fully grown, with white latex in all parts (Akinwunmi & Amadi, 2019; Bruce *et al.*, 2016). It has a white flower in a terminal inflorescence with huge, paired pods (fruits) that are yellowish when mature (Akinloye *et al.*, 2018; Aghedo *et al.*, 2021; Adegoke, Oloyede, 2013).

Even though wheat is naturally a good source of proteins (8-12%), vitamins such as vitamin E, minerals such as Iron and Zinc, and dietary fibers, a substantial part of these nutrients are lost during the milling and refining of the wheat grains for flour production (Anjum *et al.*, 2006). Furthermore, wheat lacks essential amino acids such as Lysine (Khetarpaul, Goyal, 2009). A solution to overcoming this challenge is to fortify wheat flour with *Picralima nitida* flour which is very rich in amino acids, vitamins A and E, and mineral elements like zinc, iron, and manganese (Nwaogu, 2015, Akinwunmi, Amadi, 2019). To the best of our knowledge, *Picralima nitida* flour had never been used in the formulation of composite flour with wheat. Wheat has 0 mg of cholesterol, 2 mg of sodium, and 431 mg of potassium. The total carbohydrate in 100 g of wheat is 71 g. It contains 14 g of protein with 3 % of the recommended daily dose of calcium, 20 % of vitamin B-6, 36 % of magnesium, 19 % of iron, and it contains 0 % of vitamin A, C, D, and B-12. (Nwaogu, 2015), Akinwunmi, Amadi, 2019), Awolu *et al.* (2016). Bakery foods are generally consumed worldwide due to their taste, being ready-to-eat, and convenience. Wheat is the world's third most-produced cereal and is needed as a food crop for the daily intake of proteins, vitamins, minerals, and fibers in a developing part of the global population (Awolu *et al.*, 2016). However, local pastries made from refined wheat flour have drawn negative attention due to their high-calorie content, deficiencies in essential minerals, and limited availability in certain geographical locations. In search for adequate nutritional composition of bakery products, food scientists have resorted to composite flour, which incorporates a blend of two or more

grain and non-grain flours.

A composite flour is a blend of flour made from starch-rich tubers like cassava, yams, and potatoes, as well as protein-rich flour and cereals, with or without wheat flour, that was developed to meet certain functional requirements and nutrient composition (Adefegha, Oboh, 2018). Furthermore, wheat lacks essential amino acids such as Lysine (Khetarpaul, Goyal, 2009) and is deficient in vitamins A, C, D, and B-12. However, *Picralima nitida* flour is very rich in amino acids, vitamins A and E, and mineral elements like zinc, iron, and manganese (Nwaogu, 2015; Akinwunmi & Amadi, 2019). In addition to this, previous studies showed that the consumption of fruits and vegetables correlated with a reduced risk of developing diabetes. To address this pressing public health issue, several anti-diabetic medications, including glibenclamide, metformin, and insulin, are available on the market. However, these medications often come with a hefty price tag and can cause unwanted side effects such as nausea and vomiting, as well as toxicity concerns. Despite the *Picralima nitida* fruit's potential health benefits, there is currently a lack of research supporting the development of fruits into marketable, functional food products that are ready for human consumption. Local raw materials substitution for wheat flour is increasing due to the growing market for functional foods. Thus, this study takes the initiative of evaluating the feasibility of alternative locally available fruit flour as a substitute for wheat flour. To address amino acid, protein deficiencies, and high glycemic indices in refined wheat flour. Hence, this study aims at formulating Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour blends and to investigate its glycemic indices, nutritional and antioxidant potentials.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this study include *Picralima nitida* fruit as shown in **Fig.1** and Wheat grains as seen in **Fig. 2**, which were procured randomly from Isinkan market, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The authentication of the *Picralima nitida* fruit was done at the Department of Biosciences and Biotechnology, Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, with herbarium voucher label UNIMED P.B.T.H No 0194. All reagents and chemicals used were analytical grade, while the water was glass-distilled.

Fig.1: Picture showing *Picralima nitida* fruits

Fig 2: Picture of Wheat Seeds

2.2. Preparation of samples

The *Picralima nitida* fruits (Fig. 1) and the wheat grains (Fig. 2) were washed under a jet of water to remove the dust, dirt, and any other impurities present. The washed fruits were then cut into cubes, and the wheat grains were dried in the oven at 40°C and ground to 0.5 mm pore size using an electric QASA high power blender and grinder QBL – 8008 pro-2, 230 V, 50 Hz.1000W, made in China. The powdered samples were kept in an airtight plastic container and refrigerated at 4 °C for further analysis.

The composite flours were prepared as shown in Table 1. Five blends were prepared from the composite mixture of wheat flour (WF) and *Picralima nitida* (PN) weight /weight (w/w) in the proportions of 100: 0 (100 % Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* (PN), 95: 5 (95 % WF and 5 % PN), 90: 10 (90 % WF and 10 % PN), 80: 20 (80 % WF and 20 % PN) and 70: 30 (70 % WF and 30 % PN), based on the percentage composition adopted by the method of Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.*, 2018.

Table 1: Percentage composition of Wheat - *Picralima nitida* composite flour (g / 100 g)

Composite flour	WF (g)	PN (g)
0-WN	100.00	0.00
5-WN	95.00	5.00
10-WN	90.00	10.00
20-WN	80.00	20.00
30-WN	70.00	30.00

Note: 0-WN = 100 % Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 % Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

2.3 Determination of Sugar of Wheat - *Picralima nitida* composite flour

An aliquot of 0.2 ml was obtained, and 0.5 ml (5% phenol) and 2.5 ml concentrated H₂SO₄ were added

to the supernatant after it had been decanted until it reached up to 20 ml with distilled water. This was allowed to cool, and absorbance was read at 490 nm. The method of Anthony *et al.* (2010) was used, and 0.02 g of the sample was weighed into centrifuge tubes and wet with 1 ml of ethanol. 2 ml of distilled water was added, followed by 10 ml of hot ethanol. The mixture was vortexed and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for ten minutes. The percentage of sugar was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{Sugar} = \text{Absorbance} - \frac{\text{Intercept} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \times \text{Volume}}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times \text{Slope} \times 1000$$

2.3.1 Determination of starch of Wheat - *Picalima nitida* composite flour

Perchloric acid of 7.5 ml was added to the residue obtained from sugar analysis and allowed to hydrolyze for 1 h. The mixture was then filtered through Whatman no. 2 filter papers after being diluted with 25 ml of distilled water. A sample of 0.05 ml filtrate was obtained and diluted with distilled water to make 1 ml. The solution was vortexed with 2.5 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ and 0.5 ml of phenol (5%). After standing for 10 min, the mixture was incubated for 15 min at 28°C. The absorbance was read at 490 nm. The percentage of starch was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{Starch} = \text{Absorbance} - \frac{\text{Intercept} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \times \text{Volume} \times 0.9}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times \text{Slope} \times 10000$$

2.3.2 Determination of Amylose Content of Wheat-*Picalima nitida* composite flour

Sodium hydroxide (9.2 ml of 1.0 N NaOH) was added to 0.1 g of the sample after combining it with 1.0 ml of 95% ethanol. Wheat flour was used as a reference (Deng *et al.*, 2010). The mixture was heated for 10 min at 100 °C in a water bath. Upon cooling, 0.5 cc of the diluted extract and 0.1 cc of the iodine solution (0.2% of the iodine in 2 % potassium iodide) were mixed. The test mixture was diluted to 10 ml, stirred, and left for 20 min to develop its color using distilled water. After that, the absorbance was read at 620 nm, and amylose content was calculated as shown in the equation below:

$$\% \text{Amylose} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times 0.02 \times 2500}{\text{Absorbance of standard}}$$

2.3.3 Determination of Amylopectin Content of Wheat - *Picalima nitida* composite flour

Amylopectin was calculated by subtracting the am-

yllose content from 100 % carbohydrate using the formula.

$$\% \text{Amylopectin} = 100 - \text{Amylose} (\%)$$

2.4 Determination of Estimated *In-vitro* Glycemic Index (eGI)

Fifty milligrams (50 mg) of each of the wheat-*Picalima nitida* composite flour samples were weighed into a beaker, using a JY 20002 electronic balance. Thereafter, 5 ml stomach solution (containing pepsin) of the piglets (1.5 M HCl-KCl buffer) was added and then incubated in a shaker bath for 60 min at 40 °C. It was then diluted with 7.5 mL of phosphate buffer (0.05 M, pH 6.9), and

2.5 mL α - amylase solution from porcine pancreas (Type VIB, 10 units/mg solid; CAT NO 232-565-6) was added and incubated at 37°C. Two hundred microliters (200 μL) of the digest were taken into a test tube at 30-minute intervals (0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180) min. The aliquots were boiled for 15 min before adding 500 μL of sodium acetate, pH 4.75, and followed by 5 μL of α-glucosidase from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Type I, lyophilized powder, 10 units/mg protein; CAT NO: 9001-42-7) solution, and then incubated for 45 min at 60 °C. Two hundred microliters (200 μL) of DNSA solution was added and incubated for 5 min at 100 °C, 2.0 ml of distilled water was then added, and the mixture was centrifuged for 5 min at 3000 rpm. The supernatant's absorbance was read at 540 nm (Isabel, Alejandra, and Fulgencio, 1997). The sum of the area under the curve for each of the wheat-*Picalima nitida* composite flour samples was divided by the sum of the area under the curve for standard glucose and multiplied by 100. The hydrolysis index (HI) value was obtained.

$$\text{Hydrolysis Index (HI)} = \frac{\text{Total area under the curve of the sample}}{\text{Total area under the curve of standard}} \times 100$$

The estimated *in-vitro* glycemic index (eGI) was therefore calculated using the equation:

$$\text{eGI} = 39.71 + (0.549 \text{ HI})$$

2.4.1 Determination of estimated *in-vitro* glyce-mic load

In-vitro glycemic load determines a relative indication of how much a serving of food is likely to increase blood sugar levels (Gianna *et al.*, 2016). The estimated *in-vitro* glycemic load was determined by multiplying the estimated *in-vitro* glycemic index

by the net carbohydrate divided by 100. The estimated *in-vitro* glyceamic load (eGL) is calculated

$$\text{Estimated In-vitro Glyceamic Load (eGL)} = \frac{\text{Estimated glyceamic index}}{100} \times \text{Net carbohydrate}$$

2.5 Determination of moisture content of the composite flour.

Two grams of the composite flour was weighed, dried separately at 105 °C for 4 h, and cooled in a desiccator. The samples were finally dried to a constant weight using air-oven method (AOAC, 2023). The percentage moisture content was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Weight lost } (W_2 - W_3)}{\text{Weight of sample } (W_3)} \times 100$$

W_2 = Weight of sample, W_3 = Weight of sample + Petri dish (constant weight after drying)

2.5.1 Determination of ash content of the composite flour

Two grams (2 g) of each of the samples were weighed into a dish, and the organic matter was burned off by ignition in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 5 h. Ashing continued till a constant weight was obtained. The dish containing the residue is cooled in a desiccator (AOAC, 2023). The percentage of ash content was calculated from the following equation:

$$\% \text{Ash content} = \frac{\text{Weight of ash}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.5.2 Determination of crude protein

In each of the samples, 0.2 g was weighed into a micro-Kjeldahl flask, 0.4 g of a mixed catalyst, copper (II) tetraoxosulphate (VI), and sodium tetraoxosulphate was added with 3.5 mL of concentrated tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid. Each of the samples and the content was heated on an electrical heater for 2 h (Digestion). The digested material was cooled and then placed in the distillation apparatus; 20 mL of 40 % NaOH was added, and the mixture was heated and distilled until 50 mL was collected in a 100 mL conical flask. The ammonia evolved was received in 10 mL of 2 % boric acid. The trapped ammonia was titrated against 0.02 N hydrochloric acid (HCl) using universal indicator (bromocresol green and methyl red in alcohol) (AOAC, 2023). The protein content percentage was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{Crude Protein} = \frac{\text{Molarity of HCl} \times 0.014 \times \text{titre value} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.5.3 Determination of crude fat

Two grams (2 g) of each sample were weighed and placed on a filter paper, then placed in an extraction thimble. The thimble was placed in the Soxhlet extractor, and extraction was carried out with petroleum ether (boiling point 40–60°C) for 5 h. After that, the filter papers were carefully removed and dried in an air oven at 106°C for 30 min, allowed to cool in the desiccator, and the weight was noted (AOAC, 2023). The crude fat percentage was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{Crude Fat} = \frac{\text{Loss in weight}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.5.4 Determination of crude fiber content

Freshly prepared tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid (1.25 %, 200 mL) was added to 2 g of the sample (W_1) in a 500 mL conical flask. The mixture was boiled gently for 30 min using a cooling finger to maintain a constant volume. The mixture was then filtered using a muslin cloth, and the residue was washed until it was free of acid. Two hundred milliliters of 1.25 % NaOH was added, and the mixture boiled for 30 min. The mixture was again filtered using a muslin cloth and then washed thoroughly with hot distilled water (four times) and rinsed once with 10 % HCl and four times with hot distilled water. The residue was further rinsed with ethanol and three times with petroleum ether (40–60°C boiling range) and was allowed to drain and transferred to a silica dish previously ignited at 600°C and cooled. The dish and its content were then dried to a constant weight (W_2) at 105°C. The organic matter of the residue was then burnt off by igniting in a muffle furnace at 600°C for 30 min, cooled in a desiccator, and weighed (W_3) (AOAC, 2023). The loss in ignition was reported as crude fiber, which was calculated thus:

$$\% \text{Crude Fibre} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.5.4 Carbohydrate by difference

The percentage carbohydrate contents (%) of the flour were determined by difference on dry sample weight (AOAC, 2023). The sum of the percentages of protein, crude fat, total ash content, crude fiber, and moisture content was subtracted from 100 %.

The results were then expressed on a dry weight basis.

% Carbohydrate = 100 % - (Sum of the % of moisture, ash, fat, crude fiber, and crude protein)

2.6 Mineral Analysis of Wheat-*Picralima nitida* Composite Flour

One gram (1.0 g) of each of the composite flour samples was weighed into crucibles and transferred to a muffle furnace and ashes at 550 °C until all the carbon was burnt off and the crucibles plus ash were transferred into different desiccators to cool after which 0.1M HCL solution (10 ml) was added to the crucible to break up and leach the metals. The crucible was washed three times with 0.1M HCl and made up to 100 ml with deionized water (AOAC, 2023). The mineral contents of the samples were determined using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS).

2.7 Determination of Anti-nutrients

2.7.1 Determination of phytic acid

Two grams (2 g) of fine ground of each of the samples was soaked in 100 ml of 2 % HCl for 3h and then filtered. The filtrate (25 ml) was placed in a 100 ml conical flask, and 5 ml of 0.03 % NH₄SCN solution was added as an indicator. 50 ml of distilled water was added to give it acidity. This was then titrated with ferric chloride solution, which contained 0.005 mg of Fe³⁺ per ml of FeCl₃ used; the equivalent was obtained according to the method of Young and Greaves (1940), as described by Reddy and Kove (1999), and was used to determine phytin. and from this, the phytate content in mg / 100 g was calculated:

$$\text{Phytic Acid (mg/g)} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Molarity of FeCl}_3 \times \text{Conversion Factor}}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

2.7.2 Determination of Oxalate

One gram (1 g) of the sample was weighed into a 100 ml conical flask. 75 ml of 3 M H₂SO₄ was added, and the solution was carefully stirred intermittently with a magnetic stirrer for about 1 h and then filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. 25 ml of the sample filtrate was collected and titrated hot (80 -90 °C) against 0.1 M KMnO₄ solution to the point when a faint pink color appeared and presented for at least 30 s (Day and Underwood, 1986), using the equation:

$$C_1 V_1 = C_2 V_2$$

Where C₁ and C₂ are the initial and final concentrations, while V₁ and V₂ are the initial and final volumes.

2.7.3 Determination of Saponins

The method of Obadoni and Ochuko (2001) was used; 20 g of each sample was weighed and placed in a conical flask, and 100 ml of 20 % aqueous ethanol was added. The sample was heated over a hot bath for 4 h with continuous stirring at about 55°C. The mixture was filtered, and the residue re-extracted with another 200 ml of 20 % ethanol. The combined extracts were evaporated to 40 ml over a water bath at about 90 °C. The concentrate was transferred into a 250 ml separating funnel, and 20 ml of diethyl ether was added and shaken vigorously. The aqueous layer was recovered while the ether was discarded. The purification process was repeated. 60 ml of n-butanol was added. The combined n-butanol extracts were washed twice with 10 ml of 5 % aqueous sodium chloride solution. The remaining solution was heated in a water bath. After evaporation, the sample was dried in the oven to a constant weight. The saponin content was calculated as a percentage:

$$\% \text{ Saponin} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

2.7.4 Determination of Alkaloids

Five grams (5 g) of each of the samples was weighed into a 250 ml beaker, and 200 ml of 100 % acetic acid in ethanol was added to each composite flour sample, covered, and allowed to stand for 4 h. This was filtered, and the extract was concentrated in a water bath to one-quarter of the original volume. Concentrated ammonium hydroxide was added dropwise to the extract until the precipitation was completed. The whole suspension was allowed to settle, and the precipitate was collected and washed with dilute ammonium hydroxide and then filtered (Harborne, 1993). The residue is the alkaloid, which was dried and weighed to determine the percentage composition.

$$\% \text{ Alkaloid Concentration} = \frac{\text{Weight of Alkaloid}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.8 Preparation of Aqueous Extract of the Composite Flour

The aqueous extract of each of the composite flour samples was prepared by dissolving 1g of the flour sample in 100 ml of distilled water for 6 h at 37 °C.

Thereafter, the mixture was filtered and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatants were collected and placed in a 50 ml plastic bottle, well covered, and stored in a refrigerator for further analysis. This was then used for the determination of total phenol contents, total flavonoid, and antioxidant-reducing activity (iron-reducing power content (FRAP) and nitric oxide scavenging ability) (Oboh, Adefegha, 2010).

2.8.1 Determination of total phenolic contents

The total phenolic contents of the extracts were determined using the Follin-Ciocalteu reagent (Singleton *et al.*, 1999). The extracts were diluted appropriately, neutralized in 2.0 ml of 7.5 % sodium carbonate, and oxidized in 2.5 ml of 10 % Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent (v/v). The reaction mixture was incubated for 30 min at 45 °C, and the spectrophotometer was used to measure the absorbance at 765 nm. The total phenol content was subsequently calculated using gallic acid as a standard, as shown below:

$$\text{Total Phenol (mg/g)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Concentration of standard}}{\text{Absorbance of standard} \times \text{Absorbance of sample}} \times 100$$

2.8.2 Determination of total flavonoid content

The total flavonoid concentration of the extract was assessed spectrophotometrically using the method reported by Meda *et al.* (2005). Briefly, 0.5 ml of appropriately diluted composite flour sample was mixed with 0.5 ml of methanol, 50 µL of 10 % AlCl₃, 50 µL of 1mol/L potassium acetate, and 1.4 ml of water. This was allowed to be incubated at room temperature for 30 min. After that, the reaction mixture's absorbance was measured at 415 nm. The total flavonoid was calculated using quercetin as a standard, as shown in the equation below:

$$\text{Total Flavonoid (mg/g)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Concentration of standard}}{\text{Absorbance of standard} \times \text{Concentration of sample}}$$

2.8.3 Determination of iron-reducing power content (FRAP)

Iron reducing power assay of each of the extracts was determined by the ability of the extract to reduce FeCl₃ solution according to the method described by Oyaizu (1986). A 2.5 ml aliquot was combined with 2.5 ml of 1% potassium ferricyanate and 2.5 ml of 200 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH

6.6). After 20 min of incubation at 50°C, 2.5 ml of 10 % trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added to the mixture. After 10 min, the mixture was centrifuged at 650 rpm. 5 ml of the supernatant was combined with 1 ml of 0.1 % ferric chloride and an equal amount of distilled water. A spectrophotometer was used to measure the absorbance at 700 nm using a spectrophotometer, and % FRAP was calculated using ascorbic acid and gallic acid as standard, as shown below:

$$\% \text{FRAP} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} - \text{Absorbance of Blank}}{\text{Absorbance of positive control} - \text{Absorbance of Blank}} \times 2$$

2.8.4 Determination of nitric oxide scavenging ability

Freshly prepared aqueous extract of each of the samples (100-400 µL) was added to a reaction mixture of 1000 µL freshly prepared 25 mM sodium nitrophosphide; the volume was made up to 1500 µL with distilled water, using a volumetric flask. The reaction mixture was incubated at 37°C for 2 h, and then Greiss reagent (0.1 % Sulphuric acid, 1 % phosphoric acid, and 5 % naphthyl ethylene diamine dihydrochloride) was added (Jagetia, Baliga, 2004). The absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a spectrophotometer, and the nitric oxide scavenging ability was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Nitric Oxide (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

3.0 Statistical Analysis

Graph Pad Prism version 8.0 was used for the statistical analysis. The experimental results were expressed as mean ± standard deviation of three replicates. Statistical significance, P < 0.05, was evaluated with a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

4.0 Result and Discussion

4.1 Sugar and Starch Contents of the Composite Flour

The results of the sugar and starch contents of the composite flour are presented in **Table 2**. Sugar contents of the composite flour ranged from (14.70 ± 0.04 g /100 g) to (22.21 ± 0.03 g /100 g), with the least value found in 30-WN and the highest in 0-WN. The low sugar content of the composite flour could be attributed to the inclusion of *Picalima nitida* flour in wheat flour in the production of the composite flour. The observed reduction in sugar

content of Wheat-*Picalima nitida* composite flour could help in planning safe, adequate, and effective meals and confectionery for patients suffering from malnutrition, obesity, and diabetes. The starch content results ranged from $(33.30 \pm 0.03 \text{ g} / 100 \text{ g})$ to $(44.65 \pm 0.054 \text{ g} / 100 \text{ g})$, with the least value found in 30-WN and the highest found in 0-WN. The lower starch content of the composite flour could be due to the low glycemic index of the *Picalima nitida*. The sugar/starch ratio result ranged from 30-WN (0.44) to 0-WN (0.50), with the least value found in 30-WN, while 0-WN had the highest value. The result implies that the higher the proportion of *Picalima nitida*, the lower the sugar and starch contents. The percentage sugar and the starch contents are inversely proportional to the percentage of *Picalima nitida* contents. The sugar/starch ratio of 30-WN was slightly lower than that of 0-WN. The least value of the sugar: starch ratio found in 30-WN might suggest it to be the most preferred meal for consumers living with diabetes who need low sugar/starch content in their meals.

4.1.1 Amylose and Amylopectin content evaluation of the Composite flour

The results of amylose and amylopectin, as well as those of the amylose/amylopectin ratio, are presented in Table 2. The amylose content of the composite flour followed this trend: 30-WN > 20-WN > 10-WN > 5-WN > 0-WN. It is worth noting that the amylose content was significantly higher in 30-WN than in 0-WN. It has been reported that the rheology and functional properties depend on amylose composition (Lawal *et al.*, 2011). Conversely, there was no significant difference in the composite flour's amylose content. The result of amylopectin content ranged from $(77.75^a \pm 0.94)$ to $(86.62^b \pm 1.15)$, with the least value found in 30-WN and the highest value found in 0-WN. The result of the amylopectin content of the composite flour followed the following sequential order: 0-WN > 5-WN > 10-WN > 20-WN > 30-WN. There was no significant difference in the amylopectin levels of all the flours. The lower value of amylopectin in 30-WN might slow down the hydrolysis of starch to glucose. It is recognized that digestive enzymes slowly digest amylose, whereas amylopectin is rapidly digested due to its branched structure (Giuberti *et al.*, 2015). This suggests one of the reasons why 30-WN had the least glycemic response. The findings showed that the amylose: amylopectin ratio was highest (0.29) in 30-WN and least (0.15) in 0-WN. The amylose and

amylopectin ratio of the composite flour followed the following trends: 30-WN > 20-WN > 10-WN > 5-WN > 0-WN. There is some evidence that the amylose/amylopectin ratio also affects the digestibility of starch in carbohydrate food (John *et al.*, 2009). Amylose tends to be digested more slowly and to a lesser extent than amylopectin (John *et al.*, 2009).

Values represent mean \pm Standard Deviation, $n = 3$. Values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). All values are means with different superscripts in the same row, such as a and b indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$.

Note: 0-WN = 100 %Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picalima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picalima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 %Wheat flour and 10 % *Picalima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picalima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picalima nitida* flour.

4.1.2 Estimated *In-vitro* Glycemic Index (eGI)

The composite flours estimated *in-vitro* glycemic index (eGI) and glycemic load (eGL) are presented in (Fig.1). The eGI value ranged from (28.41 ± 0.01) to (65.00 ± 0.02) , with the least value found in 30-WN and the highest found in 0-WN. The GI value followed the following sequential order: 30-WN < 20-WN < 10-WN < 5-WN < 0-WN. It was observed that as the proportion levels of *Picalima nitida* increased, the estimated glycemic index decreased. This result agrees with the findings of Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.* (2019). The glycemic index of the composite flour in our findings is lower than (40.03-46.41 %) reported for gluten-free composite flour from Wheat, Soybean, Oat-Bran, and Rice-Bran by Ijarotimi, Fakayejo, and Oluwajuyitan (2021). In 1998, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and World Health Organization (WHO) recommended low GI diets (GI of 0-55) as one of the feasible prevention tools in reducing the burden of non-communicable diseases in Africa and many other countries, medium (56-69), and high GI (greater than 70). This suggests that 30-WN might serve as a good meal in preventing and inhibiting the burden of diabetes and other non-communicable diseases. A low GI food would release glucose more slowly and steadily, leading to more suitable postprandial (after-meal) blood glucose readings (Vincent *et al.*, 2015).

Table 2: Sugar, starch, Amylose, and Amylopectin of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour

Samples	Sugar (g/100g)	Starch (g/100g)	Sugar/Starch (%)	Amylose (%)	Amylopectin (%)	Amylose/Amylopectin
0-WN	22.21 ^c ±0.03	44.65 ^c ±0.05	0.50	13.38 ^a ±2.91	86.62 ^b ±1.15	0.15
5-WN	19.18 ^b ±0.04	39.60 ^b ±0.03	0.48	17.87 ^b ±2.23	82.13 ^{ab} ±1.79	0.22
10-WN	17.15 ^{ab} ±0.01	38.17 ^b ±0.03	0.45	18.63 ^b ±2.62	81.37 ^a ±0.96	0.23
20-WN	16.07 ^{ab} ±0.04	35.60 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.45	20.50 ^{bc} ±2.16	79.50 ^a ±1.42	0.26
30-WN	14.70 ^a ±0.04	33.30 ^a ±0.03	0.44	22.25 ^c ±2.09	77.75 ^a ±0.94	0.29

High GI food would lead to an increase in blood glucose levels. It is suitable for energy recovery after exercise and is highly required to resuscitate a person experiencing hypoglycemia. **Fig. 3** shows that 30-WN had the least glycemic index (28.41±0.01), followed by 20-WN (40.08±0.03), 10-WN (43.87±0.04) and 5-WN (52.52±0.03), fall within (0-55) recommended by WHO as low glycemic diet and are therefore, regarded as low GI diets, while 0-WN (65.00±0.02) is regarded as a medium GI diet as recommended by WHO. These results agree with the GI content of pigeon-pea flour enriched with wheat flour reported by Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.* (2019). Furthermore, the GI reported in this study agrees with (22.72) reported for Soybeans by Singh *et al.* (2021). Food's glycemic effect depends on several factors, such as the type of starch, amylose versus amylopectin, fats, and protein content of the food, and organic acid and their salts in the meal (Brouns *et al.*, 2005). Adding vinegar, for example, will lower the GI (Jerkins *et al.*, 2002; Adefegha, Oboh, 2013). Consumption of low GI foods offers many health benefits including improved blood sugar control, potential weight management and a reduced risk of chronic diseases like heart disease and type -2- diabetes (Jerkins *et al.*, 2002; Adefegha, Oboh, 2013, Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.*, 2019; Singh *et al.*, 2021). Some studies suggest that low GI diets may also be beneficial for managing cholesterol levels and reducing the risk of certain cancers. Low GI foods are often rich in fiber, which may promote digestive health and help lower the risk of certain digestive disorders (Adefegha, Oboh, 2013, Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.*, 2019; Singh *et al.*, 2021).

Fig. 3: Estimated *In-Vitro* Glycemic Index of the Composite Flour

Note: 0-WN = 100 % Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 % Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

Estimated *In-vitro* Glycemic Load (eGL) is a measure of both the quality (the GI value) and quantity (grams per serve) of a carbohydrate in a meal. The GL of each composite flour was estimated by multiplying the GI value with the net carbohydrate content of the composite flour. A glycemic load of less than 20 is normal, while that above 20 is too high (Revised International Table of glycemic index and glycemic load, 2012). The estimated *in-vitro* glycemic load (eGL) shown in (Fig. 4) revealed that

30-WN, 20-WN, 10-WN and 5-WN composite flour falls within the normal range. The values of eGL ranges from (12.09^a±0.01 - 20.76^c±0.03) with the least value found in 30-WN and the highest found in 0-WN. eGL in our findings is lower than (24.64-28.50 %) reported for gluten-free composite flour from Wheat, Soybean, Oat-Bran and Rice-Bran by Ijarotimi, Fakayejo, Oluwajuyitan (2021). A higher value indicates a more rapid increase. Low GL ranges from 1 -10, Medium GL: 11-20, and High GL: 21 and above. Foods with low GL tend to be rich in fiber, protein, and healthy fats. Therefore, they may serve as a good alternative for flour production required in the formulation of adequate and functional meals for people living with diabetes. Food glyce-mic load has also been examined and reported in various African studies (Foster – Powell *et al.*, 2002; Mahgoub *et al.*, 2013). Folorunso, Olawale, Olofins, Iwaloye, (2022) worked on the ameliorates oxidative stress and modulates insulin signaling pathway of *Picralima nitida* leaf extract in high fat-diet/STZ induced diabetic rats. The study reported by the team revealed that *Picralima nitida* elevated liver enzymes, oxidative stress and impaired insulin signaling pathway associated with high-fat diet streptozotocin-induced diabetes. The team concluded that *Picralima nitida* will be of great value in the treatment of type-2 diabetes.

Osualaa, Inya-Agha, Odoh, *et al.*, (2018) and Nkoto, Kayembe, Mpiana, Ngbolua (2020). worked on *Picralima nitida* seeds and reported that the aqueous and ethanol extract contains indole alkaloids comprising akuammine (increases the sensitivity of the sympathetic nervous system to its natural artificial stimuli), akuammicine (interacts with opioid receptors), pseudoakuammigine (stimulates the central nervous system, respiration, skeletal muscle contraction and smooth muscle contraction while at high doses it inhibits them), akuammigine (reduces hypertension and renal vasoconstriction), pseudoakuammigine, akuammidine (This compound reverses the hypertensive action and suppresses the renal vasoconstrictor effects of medium doses of adrenaline; It increases hypotension caused by the initial doses of N-Ethyl-Norepinephrine and reverses the hypertensive action of medium doses of this amine). Akinwunmi, Amadi (2019) investigated the antioxidant and antidiabetic properties of *Picralima nitida* seed extracts and reported that the extracts possess significant antioxidants properties and ef-

fectively inhibit α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes. This effect is compared favourably with acarbose (a diabetes medication that slows the digestion of carbohydrates and lowers blood sugar levels. This in turns support our findings in this study that the inclusion of 30 % *Picralima nitida* in the composite flour slows the digestion of carbohydrates, lowers glycemuc index and thus, lowers the sugar contents.

More researches are needed in various countries to get population-specific data for guiding nutritionists on the formulation and production of adequate meal for patients living with diabetes. Health care practitioners also need adequate information and data on the right food types to prescribe to the individuals living with hyperglycemia. On the part of the consumers, adequate knowledge of nutritional composition, antioxidant potentials and glyce-mic of the types of food to consume is highly required for healthy living

Fig. 4: Estimated *In-vitro* Glycemic Load of the Composite Flour

Note: 0-WN = 100 % Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 % Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

4.2 Proximate Composition of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour (% DWB)

The result of proximate analysis of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour (% DWB) is shown in Table 3. The result revealed that moisture

content ranged from $(7.71^a \pm 1.03)$ to $(8.10^c \pm 0.02)$, with the least value found in 20-WN and the highest found in 0-WN. The moisture content increased with a decrease in the Carbohydrate differences of the samples and thus enhancing nutritional products. The moisture contents of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour were lower than (10.20-12.22%) reported for wheat, soy, and moringa leaf composite flour (Verem, Dooshima, Ojoutu, *et al.*, 2021). Substitution of wheat-*Picralima nitida* into wheat flour improved the moisture content of the composite flour. Ash content ranged from $(3.74^a \pm 0.01)$ to $(5.85^b \pm 0.20)$, with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest found in 30-WN. There was a significant increase in the ash content of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour as compared to 0-WN. It was noted that as the percentage proportion of *Picralima nitida* increased, the ash content increased. This connotes excellent mineral content. The findings in this study followed a similar trend with work done by Verem *et al.* (2021) on the ash contents of composite flour of wheat, soy, and moringa leaf, and sorghum and white wheat by Abdelghafor *et al.* (2011). The crude protein content ranged from $(5.83^a \pm 0.12)$ to $(9.99^b \pm 0.01)$, with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest found in 30-WN. This is lower than the protein content (15.81-21.98%) reported for composite flour blends from whole wheat, sweet potato, defatted peanut, and rice bran (Chiedu *et al.*, 2023). This may likely be due to the inclusion of defatted peanut. The composite flours were significantly higher in crude fiber $(3.71^c \pm 0.02)$ than that of wheat flour $(1.34^a \pm 0.42)$. The composite flour reported in this study is lower than the one reported by Chiedu *et al.* (2023) for fiber (7.93-10.82%) contents of the composite flour blends from whole wheat, sweet potato, defatted peanut, and rice bran. Also, the carbohydrate by differences ranged from $(63.39^a \pm 1.35)$ to $(67.85^b \pm 2.00)$. The least value was found in 30-WN, while 0-WN had the highest value. Previous studies showed that 100 g of wheat contains 339 calories, 2.5 g total fat (0.5 g of saturated fat, 1 g of polyunsaturated fat, and 0.3 g of monounsaturated fat) (Nwaogu, 2015; Akinwunmi, Amadi, 2019), Awolu *et al.* (2016). Thus, it could be deduced that as the percentage proportion of *Picralima nitida* substitution increased, there was a great improvement in the ash content, protein content, and crude fiber. Moreover, it was observed that as the proportion of *Picralima nitida* increased, there was a decrease in moisture content, fat content, and car-

bohydrate by difference. The decrease in moisture and fat contents might improve the shelf life of the composite flours.

4.3. Mineral Composition of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* Composite Flour

Food samples are generally rich in a variety of minerals (macro-minerals and trace or micro-minerals), essential for various bodily functions. The minerals are obtained from plants and animals. The macro-minerals, Sodium, Phosphorus, Calcium, Sulphur, Chloride, and Magnesium, while the trace minerals include Potassium, Zinc, Copper, Chromium, Fluoride, Iodine, Iron, Molybdenum, and Manganese. Table 4 showed that the potassium contents ranged from $212^a \pm 0.02$ to $478^c \pm 0.04$ mg/100g, with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest value found in 30-WN. The potassium content increased as the proportion of *Picralima nitida* increased. This follows the same trend with the value (1020.90 to 1044.10 mg/g) reported for wheat and plantain peel by Esan, Famuwagun, and Adeleye (2023). Potassium helps lower blood pressure by balancing out the effects of sodium and promoting healthy blood vessel function. It helps lower the risk of cardiovascular disease, including heart attacks, strokes, and cardiac arrhythmias. It helps relax muscles, supports athletic performance, promotes bone density, supports calcium balance, and regulates bowel function (Esan, Famuwagun, Adeleye, 2023). The recommended daily intake of potassium varies by age and sex. Adult men require 3400 mg/day, adult women need 2800 mg/day, and pregnant women require 2900 mg/day, while breastfeeding women require 3200 mg/day. Sodium is an essential macronutrient that plays a vital role in maintaining fluid balance, nerve, and muscle functions. It helps regulate blood pressure, supports the transport of nutrients into the cell, and maintains fluid balance. Excess sodium intake may lead to an increase in blood pressure, high risk of stroke, heart disease, and cardiovascular diseases (Mente, O'Donnell, Yusuf, 2023). The World Health Organization recommends that adults consume less than or equal to 5 g of salt daily to avoid unpleasant health challenges (Mente, O'Donnell, Yusuf, 2023). The Nutrition source lists 2300 mg a day as the maximum quantity to consume for chronic disease reduction for men and women at age 14 years and above, as well as pregnant women (Mente, O'Donnell, Yusuf, 2023). The sodium contents of Wheat – *Picralima nitida* ranged from $1.04^a \pm 0.02$ mg/100g to $1.27^a \pm 0.01$ mg/100g, with the least value found in 30-WN and the highest in

Table 3: Proximate Composition of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* Composite Flour (% DWB)

Samples	Moisture	Ash (%)	Crude Fat	Crude Pro-	Crude-fiber	Carbohydrate
0-WN	8.10 ^{bc} ±0.02	3.74 ^a ±0.01	13.14 ^c ±1.01	5.83 ^a ±0.12	1.34 ^a ±0.42	67.85 ^b ±2.00
5-WN	7.84 ^b ±0.11	5.71 ^b ±0.12	9.82 ^b ±0.00	9.40 ^b ±0.15	2.14 ^b ±0.21	65.59 ^{ab} ±1.48
10-WN	7.86 ^b ±0.01	5.76 ^b ±0.12	9.40 ^a ±0.05	9.58 ^b ±0.61	2.17 ^b ±0.02	65.23 ^a ±1.11
20-WN	7.71 ^a ±1.03	5.76 ^b ±0.20	9.37 ^a ±1.04	9.77 ^b ±0.01	2.70 ^b ±0.01	64.69 ^a ±1.20
30-WN	7.72 ^a ±0.14	5.85 ^b ±0.20	9.34 ^a ±0.20	9.99 ^b ±0.01	3.71 ^c ±0.02	63.39 ^a ±1.35

Note: Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation, n = 3. Values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different (P<0.05). All values are means with different superscripts in the same row, such as a, b indicate significant differences at P < 0.05 based on ANOVA with Tukey's test on retention D-2.

Key: 0-WN = 100 %Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 %Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

Table 4: Mineral Composition of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* Composite Flour

Samples	Potassium (mg/100g)	Sodium (mg/100g)	Calcium (mg/100g)	Magnesium (mg/100g)	Zinc (mg/100g)	Iron (mg/100g)	Copper (mg/100g)	Manganese (mg/100g)
0-WN	212 ^a ±0.02	1.27 ^a ±0.01	12.00 ^a ±0.00	102 ^a ±0.02	1.04 ^a ±0.00	0.28 ^a ±0.01	0.46 ^a ±0.11	0.10 ^a ±0.00
5-WN	322 ^b ±0.11	1.15 ^a ±0.02	186 ^b ±0.00	196 ^a ±0.01	1.86 ^b ±0.15	0.29 ^a ±0.01	0.61 ^a ±0.00	0.10 ^a ±0.00
10-WN	405 ^{bc} ±0.01	1.12 ^a ±0.12	286 ^b ±0.05	246 ^a ±0.11	1.94 ^b ±0.01	0.31 ^a ±0.02	0.62 ^a ±0.05	0.18 ^a ±0.00
20-WN	445 ^c ±0.03	1.10 ^a ±0.02	288 ^b ±0.04	248 ^a ±0.12	2.13 ^b ±0.01	0.40 ^a ±0.01	0.64 ^a ±0.12	0.21 ^a ±0.00
30-WN	478 ^c ±0.04	1.04 ^a ±0.02	290 ^b ±0.03	259 ^a ±0.31	2.16 ^b ±0.01	0.42 ^a ±0.02	0.67 ^a ±0.15	0.25 ^a ±0.00

Note: Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation, n = 3. Values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different (P<0.05). All values are means with different superscripts in the same row, such as a, b indicate significant differences at P < 0.05 based on ANOVA with Tukey's test on retention D-2.

Key: 0-WN = 100 %Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 % Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

0-WN. It was observed that as the proportion of *Picralima nitida* increased, the sodium content decreased. Calcium is a major mineral that plays a vital role in building, maintaining, and supporting strong bones, teeth, muscle function, nerve transmission, and blood clotting. Adequate calcium intake is associated with lower blood pressure among the youth, prevention of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, lower cholesterol values, and prevention of renal stones and colorectal adenomas. (Cormick, Betran, Romero, *et al.*, 2021). The calcium content of Wheat-*Picralima nitida* ranged from 12.00^a±0.00 to 290^b±0.03 mg/100g, with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest in 30-WN. It was observed that as the proportion of *Picralima nitida* increased, the calcium content of the flour also increased. Sofonyas, Neela, Agimassie *et al.* (2024) reported the same trend for pearl millet, teff, and buckwheat grain composite flour (72.82–93.14 mg/100g). There was a great improvement in the nutritional composition of Wheat *Picralima-nitida* than that

reported by Sofonyas, Neela, Agimassie *et al.* (2024) for pearl millet, teff, and buckwheat grain composite flour. The magnesium contents of the composite flour improved greatly with increased proportions of *Picralima nitida* substituted in wheat flour. The values ranged from (102^a±0.02-259^a±0.31 mg/100g), with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest found in 30-WN. The content observed in the current study improved the magnesium content than the reported value of (78±0.67 mg/100g) for rice-based composite flour by Basseyy, Nchor, Ime, *et al.* (2023). This may be attributed to high contents of magnesium and calcium in *Picralima nitida* powder. Magnesium is a crucial mineral that supports various bodily functions, encompassing blood sugar regulation, muscle and nerve function, and reducing the risk of cardiovascular diseases. National Institutes of Health – Office of Dietary Supplements reported that Magnesium plays a major role in regulating the nervous system, which may help with mood, sleep, and reduce anxiety and

depression. It may help lower high blood pressure levels and reduce the risk of heart disease. Magnesium plays a vital role in bone formation, maintenance, and helps in keeping bones strong and dense.

Zinc is an essential mineral that plays a vital role in various bodily functions. Zinc helps to activate immune cells, and it has antimicrobial properties, which help to fight off bacterial, viral, and fungal infections. Zinc has anti-inflammatory properties and activates collagen synthesis, which helps to reduce inflammation, promote wound healing, and tissue repair. It is essential for maintaining healthy skin, hair, and nails. The recommended daily intake of zinc varies by age and sex. National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Dietary Supplements (ODS) recommends the following daily intake of Zinc: Adult men require 11 mg/day, adult women need 8 mg/day, pregnant women require 11-12 mg/day, and breastfeeding women need 12-13 mg/day. Zinc content of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* follows this sequential order:

30 – WN > 20 – WN > 10 – WN > 5 – WN > 0 – WN

The content observed in this study aligns closely with the findings of Sofonyas, Neela, Agimassie *et al.* (2024) that a blend of 70 % teff, 20 % buckwheat, and 10 % pearl millet composite flour offers improved nutritional properties. Iron, copper, and manganese contents of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour ranged from (0.28^a±0.01 - 0.42^a±0.02 mg/100g), (0.46^a±0.11 - 0.67^a±0.15 mg/100g), (0.10^a±0.00 - 0.25^a±0.00 mg/100g). The nutritional composition of iron, copper, and manganese improved as the percentage proportions of *Picralima nitida* increased in the composite flour. This may be due to the high content of Zinc, Iron, and Manganese present in *Picralima nitida* powder.

4.4 Antinutrients Composition of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* Composite Flour

Anti-nutrients are compounds that can interfere with the absorption of nutrients in the body. Anti-nutrients of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour (% DWB) mg/100g are shown in **Table 5**. Tannin content of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour ranged from 7.38^a±0.01 to 17.24^b±0.02 mg/100g, with the lowest value found in 0-WN and the highest found in 30-WN. The trend followed this sequential order:

30 – WN > 20 – WN > 10 – WN > 5 – WN > 0 – WN.

Tannins are a type of polyphenol, a class of compounds found in plants. They are known for their

astringent, bitter taste and ability to bind to proteins and other molecules. The current study revealed that as the proportion of *Picralima nitida* in the composite flour increased, the tannin content increased. This could be attributed to the bitterness of the *Picralima nitida* flour. The oxalate content ranged from (1.10^a±0.01 to 1.40^a±0.03 mg/100g), with the highest value found in 30-WN and the lowest value found in 0-WN. Oxalates are a type of organic acid that can bind to minerals like Calcium, Magnesium, and Iron, making them less available for absorption. As the proportion of *Picralima nitida* increased, the oxalate content decreased. Excess oxalate consumption may increase the risk of developing kidney stones, binding to minerals, making them less available for absorption. Phytate content ranged from 0.06^a±0.00 to 0.16^a±0.00 mg/100g, with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest found in 30-WN. Phytates, known as phytic acid, are a type of phosphorus compound that can bind to minerals like zinc, iron, calcium, and magnesium, making them less available for absorption (Vilanculos, Svanberg, 2021). There was no significant difference in the saponin of the composite flour and that of wheat flour. The alkaloid content of the wheat flour was significantly lower than that of the composite flour. Alkaloids are a type of heterocyclic compound that contains nitrogen. They are found in plants, where they play a role in defense, growth, and development (Vilanculos, Svanberg, 2021).

4.5 Evaluation of Phenolic and Flavonoid Contents of the Composite Flour

The results of the total phenol content [reported as milligram gallic acid equivalent (mg GAE)] and the entire flavonoid contents of the composite flour are shown in **Table 6**. The results of the total phenol content ranged from (510.75±1.90 mg GAE /100 g) to (1376.50±3.08 mg GAE / 100 g), with the lowest value found in 0-WN, while the highest value was found in 30-WN. The entire phenol contents of all the composite flours were significantly higher (P < 0.05) than that of wheat flour. The total phenol contents of flour results followed this sequential trend: 30-WN > 20-WN > 10-WN > 5-WN > 0-WN. The flavonoid contents of the composite flour ranged from (281.40±2.19 mg QE/100 g) to (551.81±2.56 mg QE/100 g), with the least value found in 0-WN and the highest found in 30-WN. The result follows this sequential order: 30-WN > 20-WN > 10-WN > 5-WN > 0-W. It was observed that the composite flour had higher flavonoid content than the wheat flour. Recent findings have shown that the health-promoting

Table 5: Antinutrients of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* Composite Flour (% DWB) mg/100g

Sample	Tannin (mg/100g)	Oxalate (mg/100g)	Phytate (mg/100g)	Saponin (%)	Alkaloid (%)
0-WN	7.38 ^a ±0.01	1.40 ^a ±0.03	0.06 ^a ±0.00	2.00 ^a ±0.00	7.00 ^a ±0.00
5-WN	14.81 ^b ±0.11	1.21 ^a ±0.02	0.06 ^a ±0.00	2.02 ^a ±0.01	8.00 ^a ±0.01
10-WN	15.07 ^b ±0.04	1.13 ^a ±0.02	0.14 ^a ±0.00	2.04 ^a ±0.01	10.00 ^{ab} ±0.02
20-WN	16.14 ^b ±0.12	1.11 ^a ±0.01	0.88 ^a ±0.01	2.07 ^a ±0.01	11.50 ^{ab} ±0.21
30-WN	17.24 ^b ±0.02	1.10 ^a ±0.01	0.16 ^a ±0.00	2.10 ^a ±0.01	12.01 ^{ab} ±0.02

Note: Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation, n = 3. Values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different (P<0.05). All values are means with different superscripts in the same row, such as a, b indicate significant differences at P < 0.05 based on ANOVA with Tukey's test on retention D-2.

Key: 0-WN = 100 %Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 %Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

Table 6: The total phenol, total flavonoid content (mg QE /100 g), FRAP (mmol AAE/g), and Nitric oxide scavenging ability of the composite flour extracts

Samples	Total phenol (mg GAE /100 g)	Total Flavonoid content (mg)	FRAP (mmol AAE/g)	Nitric oxide scavenging ability (%)
0-WN	510.75 ^a ±1.90	281.40 ^a ±2.19	39.05 ^a ±1.92	30.34 ^a ±0.01
5-WN	641.59 ^{ab} ±2.06	366.18 ^b ±0.93	47.60 ^b ±2.87	30.78 ^a ±0.01
10-WN	852.00 ^b ±2.05	421.74 ^{bc} ±1.33	48.82 ^b ±2.56	33.10 ^b ±0.06
20-WN	1065.50 ^c ±3.07	439.45 ^{bc} ±2.09	57.36 ^{bc} ±1.33	33.22 ^b ±0.03
30-WN	1376.50 ^d ±3.08	551.81 ^c ±2.56	70.78 ^c ±1.78	33.56 ^b ±0.05

Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation, n = 3. Values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different (P<0.05). All values are means with different superscripts in the same row, such as a and b indicating significant differences at P < 0.05.

Note: 0-WN = 100 % Wheat flour (WF) and 0 % *Picralima nitida* flour (PN), 5-WN (95 %Wheat flour and 5 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 10-WN = 90 %Wheat flour and 10 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 20-WN = 80 %Wheat flour and 20 % *Picralima nitida* flour, 30-WN = 70 %Wheat flour and 30 % *Picralima nitida* flour.

effects of medicinal plants may be associated with their phenolic constituents (Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.*, 2018). Flavonoids have antioxidant activity and could, therefore, lower cellular oxidative stress, which has been implicated in the pathogenesis of various neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.*, 2018). These results showed that all the composite flours produced are rich in flavonoids and phenols. The FRAP and Nitric Oxide ranged from (39.05^a±1.92 to 70.78^c±1.78 mmol AAE/g) and (30.34^a±0.01 to 33.56^b±0.05 %) respectively. The high flavonoid and total phenol contents of *Picralima nitida* might have contributed to the improved antioxidant potentials of the composite flour. There was an agreement between the total phenol and total flavonoid contents of all the composite flours produced. This finding agrees with many earlier reports where correlations were established between total phenol and entire flavonoid contents (Obboh, Adefeigha, 2010; Melo *et al.*, 2006; Obboh, Rocha, 2008; Gbenga-Fabusiwa *et al.*, 2018). Complete knowledge about the therapeutic role of dietary phenolic antioxidants would be needed to develop functional foods. Phenolic antioxidants are the most abundant antioxidants in human diets.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

Picralima nitida is a highly nutritious medicinal plant, but bitter in taste. The results from this work have shown that all the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flours had low sugar, low starch, and low carbohydrate by difference. The study also reveals that as the substitution of the percentage proportion of *Picralima nitida* in wheat flour increases, the crude fiber, protein content, and the ash content of the composite flour also increase. The study also establishes the fact that the percentage proportion of *Picralima nitida* is inversely proportional to the percentage proportion of sugar and starch contents. It is observed that the estimated glycemic index and glycemic load are lowered by adding 30 % *Picralima nitida* to wheat flour. Therefore, 70% Wheat flour fortified with 30 % *Picralima nitida* (30-WN) may be the most suitable composite flour for people living with type-2-diabetes.

The inclusion of the *Picralima nitida* in the composite flour improves the antioxidant potential of the composite flour, with outstanding results found in 30-WN. Formulation of 30-WN might be richer in antioxidants needed to fight free radicals in the body. This could enhance the potential of the Wheat-*Picralima nitida* flours as anti-diabetic diets. Thus, suggesting the 30-WN composite flour blend, a promising functional food that could help to fight free radicals in the bodies of people living with diabetes.

Furthermore, the production of Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour blends may provide a platform for further developing high-value functional food products like *Picralima nitida* bread, biscuit, and amala, utilizing them as a dietary intervention in diabetes type -2 management. *Picralima nitida* may serve as a good source of functional food in formulating Wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour due to its high protein and crude fiber content.

5.2 Recommendation

The data generated in this study may provide valuable information on the processes involved in formulating, planning, and utilizing high-quality wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour as a viable substitute for wheat flour, which is not produced domestically in Nigeria. This will also enhance the full utilization of *Picralima nitida* and global cultivation. High-quality wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite

flour formulated in this study could suggest the possibility of producing wheat-*Picralima nitida* flour on a large scale as a viable substitute for wheat flour in confectioneries.

This study so far is based on assessing the nutritional, antioxidant potentials, and glycemic indices of wheat-*Picralima nitida* composite flour; however, clinical trials of the flour samples should be carried out to determine their dosage and utilization in the food industry.

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